

NET_CITY:

A collaborative environment to promote the understanding of the contemporary city

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Abstract

We have carried out a pedagogic experience, in which citizens and students of architecture -working on a web environment especially designed for this project (<http://www.salleurl.edu/illamyurgia>)- collaboratively construct an understanding of the environment they live in. Through the web, any person can submit his or her view of the urban environment by means of a concept, a text and an image. Ad-hoc interfaces for collaborative work allows students to analyze that information, establishing relationships between the data items, and developing lines of argument from them. In this context, the application of information technologies enables us to eliminate existing boundaries (individual, social, cultural, political, disciplinary), and to create new spaces of interaction and communication. We believe that a new vision of the city might emerge from this collaborative analysis; a vision that is conceived and expressed through a new language: the language of the communication and information media.

1. Introduction

Citizen's participation is a valuable factor in the development of a city. Since 1960, neighbors' associations have played an important role in the transformation of Barcelona. The strong identity of citizens with their neighborhoods has had its counterpart in the urban structure of the city: for many decades, Barcelona has been formally developing as a structure of neighborhoods. However, in the last decade, the scale of the city has radically changed: it is becoming one more node in the network of world cities. As a result, the neighborhood might no longer be that part of the city that the citizen recognizes as a distinctive area (morphologically, sociologically). Rather, the city as a whole is now considered one neighborhood in a global city of imprecise limits and unknown center. Not only the limits of the city are blurring, but also the modes of perception are changing. Direct experience of the urban environment no longer suffices. The image of the city that is forged through the media (tourist brochures, advertisement, Internet) is also contributing to shape our understanding of it.

If we want citizens to keep playing a meaningful role in the urban transformation process, it is necessary to make them aware of the new dimensions that the urban environment is acquiring. Moreover, in order to grasp those dimensions, they need to understand the city through the modes of perception that are peculiar to contemporary culture.

With these purposes, we organized the Workshop on Urban Perception in the summer semester of 2001, in Barcelona. The workshop, carried out over two weeks, consisted of lectures dealing with the different modes of perceiving and representing the city over history, along with exercises on urban perception which students and citizens would carry out collaboratively using ITC. As a case study, we took the renewal of a block in the neighborhood of Sagrada Familia, called Illa Myrurgia.

2. The modes of perception of the city

2.1. The city as form

A city cannot be apprehended as a totality. First of all, being a city the space of our existence, it is difficult for us to detach from it and see it as an object. Also, because of its dimensions, we can never gain a whole view of a city as a whole. We can only have partial glimpses from which we construct an overall image; an image which is determined by our experience of the city as well as by our modes of perception.

The modes of perception very much determined our understanding of the city. In his book, *Der Städtebau nach seinen künstlerischen Grundsätzen*, 1889, Camilo Sitte considered the city to be a work of art and not just a

technical problem; a work which should move the beholder because of the harmonic relationships between built form and open space. However, Sitte was not so much concerned with the city as a totality as with only those that could be contemplated, like the squares and the streets¹. He understood space as a dynamic element, loaded with a visual energy which could be contained or conducted by the location of buildings and monuments. Sitte criticized the cities of his time, because they lacked any relationship between built form and public space, and because their spaces had neither function nor meaning². The middle-age city, he claimed, would be the model to imitate, in so far as it united building form, open space and function, in a harmonic manner. The beholder that Sitte had in mind was a walking spectator having the sensitivity to feel how space flows from a square into the adjacent streets, being able to appreciate a picturesque vista.

Later on, in his book *The Image of the City*, 1964, Kevin Lynch was concerned with the intelligibility of the city's overall shape. For Lynch, the pleasure that a city produces is directly related with its "readability", that is to say, with the facility with which its parts can be recognized and organized in a coherent structure.³ This structure, according to Lynch, is made up of five structural elements: paths, borders, districts, nodes, landmarks, and districts. The image of the city is collectively created⁴. In this regard, Lynch is not concerned with the individual beholder, as Sitte, but with the collective inhabitant. Moreover, this underlying structure (e.g. the image) must be shared by the inhabitants of the city and by the city planners. Accordingly, the best planned city would be such in which the image that inhabitants can build from it matches the image that the designers had in mind. While Sitte was mainly concerned with picturesque views of concrete city spots, Lynch is more concerned with the intelligible form that underlies the visual appearances.

Both, Sitte and Lynch, considered that their contemporary cities were not properly designed, and their respective modes of perception are also meant to be modes of conception/production which would bring about the harmonic or intelligible urban spaces they considered to be the aesthetic ideal. In contrast to this negative view of the contemporary city, Robert Venturi et al, postulated in *Learning from Las Vegas* that the urban sprawl and the commercial strip of the American city were not errors that had to be amended. The modern city was fine, since it had naturally developed in response to the needs it had to fulfill, so all what architects and planners had to do was to learn from it: "Learning from the existing landscape is a way of being revolutionary for an architect. Not the obvious way, which is to tear down Paris and begin again, as Le Corbusier suggested in the 1920's, but another, more tolerant way; that is, to question how we look at things" (p.3) To learn to look at things differently it was necessary a new sensitivity to understand the city ("The graphic sign in space has become the architecture of this landscape....The sign is more important than the architecture." P.13) and that "the sign is more important than the architecture" and new modes of abstraction to represent it –that is to say, to understand it.⁵

2.2. The city as experience

In contrast to the notion of a city as object (formal, spatial), the situationists of the 1960's defended the importance of the experience of the subject in the perception of the city. For them, it was not relevant that the perception of the city would lead to a coherent or harmonic image in the mind of the beholder. Rather, the opposite was true. For the situationists, the subject should be free from all preconceptions (all mental images), in order to get surprised by the city spaces (derive). Also, our experience of space should not be conditioned by the daily activities, but we should give new meaning to space inventing situations.

¹ "Künstlerisch wichtig ist nur dasjenige, was überschaubar, was gesehen werden kann; also die einzelne Straße, der einzelne Platz." Sitte, *Der Städtebau*, p. 101.

² "...in künstlerischer Beziehung ist ein bloß unverbaute Fleck noch kein Stadtplatz. Strenggenommen gehört von diesem Standpunkte aus sogar sehr viel noch dazu an Ausschmückung, Bedeutung, Charakter." Ibid. p. 38.

³ "facilidad con la que pueden reconocerse y organizarse sus partes en una pauta coherente". Lynch, *La imagen de la ciudad*, p. XX.

⁴ "Cada individuo crea y lleva su propia imagen, pero parece existir una coincidencia fundamental entre los miembros de un mismo grupo. Son estas imágenes colectivas, que demuestran el consenso entre números considerables de individuos, las que interesan a los urbanistas que aspiran a modelar un medio ambiente que será usado por gran número de personas." Ibid. p. XX.

⁵ "The representation techniques learned from architecture and planning impede our understanding from Las Vegas. They are static where it is dynamic, contained where it is open, two-dimensional where it is three-dimensional....Architectural techniques are suitable for large, broad objects in space, like buildings, but not for thin, intense objects, like signs; planning techniques are able to depict activity (land use), but in excessively general categories, for the ground floor only, and without intensity." Venturi, p.75.

About the same time, Italo Calvino vindicated in *Invisible Cities*, 1972, the importance of a collective memory in the perception of the city⁶. For Calvino, the city is not an object made of other objects: "*Las ciudades son un conjunto de muchas cosas: memorias, deseos, signos de un lenguaje*".⁷ Rather, the city is made of relationships between the dimensions of its spaces and the events of its past.⁸ A city is the depository of a collective memory, the expression of a collective subconscious lying in everyone's mind. It is this collective archetype that then enables us to discover the cities that we will meet: "*cada hombre lleva en su mente una ciudad hecha sólo de diferencias, una ciudad sin figuras y sin forma, y las ciudades particulares la rellenan*".⁹ In a poetic manner, Calvino reminds us of the time dimension of the city is not constrained to the actual, the time the inhabitant that perceives its spaces, its image. To perceive the city means also to understand its past; its memory.

2.3. The city as media

Marshall McLuhan had once contended that "The city no longer exists, except as a cultural ghost for tourists". In our media society, the image of the city does not emerge only from the direct experience of the beholder. Through the media (cinema, advertisement, television), a city can become an object of experience, without having ever visited it. Moreover, with the development of the tourism industry, it has become crucial for cities to appear as icons or symbols in the media (e.g. the Sagrada Familia and the Olympic Games as the icon and the symbol of Barcelona). Most cities have looked for these identity signs in their past. Typically, the old parts of cities fulfill the role of giving visual identity to a place (the interest for preservation the nineteenth century district of Barcelona, l'Eixample, has grown in parallel to the increase of the number of tourists visiting the city). In the absence of an effective historical sign, cities turn to modern architecture to create one (e.g. Bilbao's Guggenheim).

Therefore, besides existing in a collective memory, as Calvino wrote, cities also exist nowadays in the reality of the media. As Baudrillard has explained it: "Through reproduction from one medium into another the real becomes volatile, it becomes the allegory of death, but it also draws strength from its own destruction, becoming the real for its own sake, a fetishism of the lost object which is no longer the object of representation, but the ecstasy of the degeneration and its own ritual extermination: the hyper real."¹⁰ Modern cities exist today as realities detached from their own memory, from their own history, from their own inhabitants: they have become lost objects in the realm of the hyper reality.

2.4 The city as network

According to Paul Virilio, a city would be a form of occupation of space, whose shape would be determined by the techniques that facilitate the communication between distant points. The city, therefore, is the place of proximity between people, the place to organize contact. The proximity can be 'instantaneous', as in the agora or forum; 'mechanical', as in a territory connected by trains; and 'electromagnetic', like in the computer networks that facilitate the contact in real time, between geographically distant places.¹¹

Today's cities, Virilio argues, can no longer be seen as autonomous, well-defined entities but as formless nodes being part of a network; a network with a virtual hipercenter around which cities can only made the periphery¹². The space of influence of a city is no longer limited by its physical boundaries. This network of

⁶ "(Zora) Esta ciudad que no se borra de la mente es como un armazón o una retícula en cuyas casillas cada uno puede disponer las cosas que quiere recordar: nombres de varones ilustres, virtudes, números, clasificaciones vegetales y minerales, fechas de batallas, constelaciones, partes del discurso. Entre cada noción y cada punto del itinerario podrá establecer un nexo de afinidad o de contraste que sirva de llamada instantánea a la memoria." Italo Calvino, *Las ciudades invisibles*, pp. 30-31.

⁷ Ibid. p. 15.

⁸ "La ciudad no está hecha de eso, sino de relaciones entre las medidas de su espacio y los acontecimientos de su pasado". Ibid. p. 25.

⁹ Ibid. p. 47

¹⁰ Jean Baudrillard, *Symbolic Exchange and Death*

¹¹ Virilio, *El Ciber mundo*

¹² Virilio: "El suburbio y el centro-ciudad son sustituidos por ciudades-suburbio con referencia a la GLOBAL CITY. Paralelamente a esta metropolización, aparece un hipercentro, una metaciudad, una ciudad virtual que existe gracias a la urbanización de las telecomunicaciones y que se está gestando en las autopistas electrónicas. Esta ciudad está por todas partes y por ninguna a la vez, y cada una de las ciudades-mundo es un barrio, un cinturón de esa hiper ciudad que parece el espejismo virtual de la economía." (*El Ciber mundo*)

cities is everywhere and nowhere, it has no shape and no center, its existence is only manifested by the activities occurring within the network.¹³

The impact that communication and information technologies have in the shape of cities has also been addressed by William Mitchell in *City of Bits*, 1996. The city that Mitchell envisions is the result of the intertwining between the physical and technological realms: "This will be a city unrooted to any definite spot on the surface of the earth, shaped by connectivity and bandwidth constraints rather than by accessibility and land values, largely asynchronous in its operation, and inhabited by disembodied and fragmented subjects who exist as collections of aliases and agents. Its places will be constructed virtually by software instead of physically from stones and timbers, and they will be connected by logical linkages rather than by doors, passageways and streets." The inhabitant of the *City of Bits* would be no longer interested to discover a picturesque vista while walking through the city, as in Sitte, or to understand its total shape, as in Lynch¹⁴. Rather, the new city will give rise to a new sort of inhabitant: a cyborg citizen: "We are all cyborgs now. Architects and urban designers of the digital era must begin by retheorizing the body in space."¹⁵

According to Mitchell, technology would be the driving force behind the transformation of the physical shape of cities. For example, computer-based technology would make unnecessary certain types of buildings –like banks, bookstores, and libraries- because the activities that are taking place in this building would take place in the computer networks.

Manuel Castells, in *The Informational City*, 1989, considers technology as "mediators", rather than as direct cause of change: "New information technologies are transforming the way we produce, consume, manage, live, and die; not by themselves, certainly, but as powerful mediators of the broader set of factors that determines human behavior and social organization".¹⁶ He distinguishes between two kinds of space –the space of flows, and the space of places¹⁷. The first one adopts the configuration of a network, through which goods and information circulate in the most efficient manner. The second one is the space where people actually live, those places that are perceptually and experientially meaningful for an individual ("People live in places, power rules through flows", p.349). Castells sees that in the contemporary society the space of flows is superseding the space of places, resulting in a loss of cultural values: "At the cultural level, local societies, territorially defined, must preserve their identities, and build upon their historical roots, regardless of their economic and functional dependence upon the space of flows."¹⁸

A city which is the expression of the space of flows, rather than of the space of places, would be a shapeless city; a city with no visual identity, and no recognizable limits. In fact, the victory of the space of flows over the space of places might bring about the disappearance of the city and of architecture as we have understood it. And it might lead as well to a change of aesthetics, to a new aesthetic of disappearance, as Virilio has called it: "The disappearance not only affects architecture but any kind of materiality: the earth (deterritorialization), the body (disembodiment) and architecture (deconstruction-in the literal sense of the word, not the architectural style). Any kind of matter is about to vanish in favor of information. You can see it also as a change of aesthetics. To me, to disappear does not mean to become eliminated. Just like the Atlantic, which continues to be there even though you can no longer feel it as you fly over it. Or like the body that continues to exist without actually being needed -since we just switch the channel. The same happens with architecture: it will continue to exist, but in the state of disappearance".¹⁹

3. Pedagogic objectives

¹³ Virilio: "esta ciudad local ya sólo es un BARRIO, un distrito más de la invisible METACIUDAD MUNDIAL, cuyo centro está en cualquier parte y su circunferencia en ninguna."(*El Cibermundo*)

¹⁴ "We are beginning to know and use cities in new ways. Long ago the theorist Kevin Lynch pointed out the fundamental relationship between human cognition and urban form –the importance of the learned mental maps that knowledgeable locals carry about inside their skulls. These mental maps, together with the landmarks and edges that provide orientation within the urban fabric, are what make a city seem familiar and comprehensible. But for us artificially intelligent cyborgs, the ability to navigate through the streets and gain access to a city's resources isn't all in our heads. Increasingly, we rely on our electronic extensions –smart vehicles and hand-held devices, together with the invisible landmarks provided by electronic positioning systems- to orient us in urban fabric, to capture and process knowledge of our surroundings, and to get us to where we want to go." Mitchell. p. 43.

¹⁵ Ibid. p. 28.

¹⁶ Castells, *The Informational City*, p.15.

¹⁷ "We can see a major social trend standing out from all our observations: the historical emergence of the space of flows, superseding the meaning of the space of places." Ibid. p. 348.

¹⁸ Ibid. p. 350.

¹⁹ Virilio, p.XX

The theories we have summarized above were explained in class to the students participating in the seminar. The goal of the workshop was to integrate this theoretical background with a practical experience of urban analysis, carried out collaboratively by students and citizens using information and communication technologies.

The study case was the transformation of an old factory in a block of the district of Sagrada Familia called Illa Myrurgia. The conversion of the existing structure into condominiums had been contested by neighbor associations, who wanted instead more social housing and more public facilities. Considering the level of engagement of the citizens in the public debate, we thought this to be the right scenario to carry out a collaborative workshop.

Meetings with local representatives were held to inform them about the purposes of the workshop, which was advertised in the neighborhood with flyers sent by post to the members of the local associations, and posted around the neighborhood (Figure 1). In these flyers, we asked citizens the following questions about their urban environment: what would you consider to be the most representative element of your neighborhood (a monument, a street, a square.....)?; where would you place the limits of your urban space (a building, a street.....)?; which is your personal experience of the public spaces you normally use?; what are you missing in your neighborhood that makes you move to another place to find it?; in which kind of space does your social activity normally take place?; what do you think of the use that people make of the public space (how the move through it, how they stand on it)? , and, which objects would you stand out in the urban environment (a sign, a color, a facade....)?

Figure 1. Brochure distributed in the neighborhood.

Citizens were expected to send their contributions, through the web, using a web-based system especially developed for the project. Our pedagogic objective was to apply ITC to develop new spaces of learning, transcending the boundaries that separate university from society. The goal of this initiative was to create a learning space in which citizens, students and professors would collaborate to build an understanding of their urban environment.

4. Web-based environment

Figure 2. Structure of the web environment.

The web-based learning system we have created is structured into three environments (Figure 2): 1. the outer one (Environment Citizen), where any citizen can submit a contribution and have access to the ideas and opinions introduced by any Internet user participating in the project; 2. the inner one (Environment Student), where students organize the information received through Internet in topics and lines of debate; and 3. an in-between interface (Environment Student: Citizen), where students and citizens exchange their views of the urban environment. Besides, there is an Environment Administrator where the flow of information between the different environments is managed.

4.1 Environment Citizen

The home page is divided into two windows. The project information is described on the background window. On the foreground, a small viewer displays all the information, sequentially (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Home page of the project Illa Myrurgia.

The information displayed in the viewer can be organized in different categories: “A”, by alphabetical order; “V”, by degree of interest (a value which is assigned by the project coordinators), and “N”, by date of submission. Also, it is possible to display a particular item selecting it by its name in a list (Figure 4). The user can let the system display the information (images and texts) automatically (this is the default option) or alternatively, look for the item he or she is interested in. Also, the user can gain control over the automatic display in order to move forward or backwards at will. When the user wants to add a contribution to an existing item, he or she must click on the icon “...” to open the input form. To start a new theme, the user must click on “T” to get a similar input form. In both cases, the information requested is a short text, and image (optional) and the name of theme (if it is a new one).

Figure 4. Selecting an item in the list.

Figure 5. Input form to add a contribution.

4.2 Environment Student: Citizen

In this environment, students and citizens participate in the construction of lines of debate (Figure 6). To start a line of debate it is necessary to give it a name, a short description and an image. The proposed themes, represented by their corresponding icons, are displayed on the horizontal line at the top. Other participants can add new items to an existing line of debate. To visualize all the items of a line of debate, the icon must be clicked on so that images and texts are displayed in the main window.

Figure 6. A line of debate in the environment Student: Citizen

To be able to express properly an idea in this context, participants must understand the characteristics of the media they are working with. Images must be rich in meanings; texts must be clear and concise; and text and images must complement each other to convey a communicable idea. Associative thinking also intervenes in the collaborative construction of a line of debate. Images and texts must be eloquent enough to induce to other participants to continue developing ideas from them. In this exchange process, both citizens and students must make the effort to become intelligible to each other, by means of a common language.

4.3 Environment Student

In this environment students introduce items into the system and create new lines of debate combining them with the items sent by citizens through Internet. Students can introduce four kinds of item (DATOS): texts, images, videos and sounds (Figure 7).

Each one of these four formats is meant to be perceptual mechanism to capture the urban environment. This way of structuring the information as data channels enables us to see the city represented as text, image, motion and sound. One step further is to combine these items in lines of argumentation. A line of argumentation is created on a window that displays all existing items as icons. To create a line, the icons must be dragged to the hot area at the bottom of the window (Figure 8). Afterwards, it opens up a second window where the student must explain the image of the city that these items (an image, a sound) evoke. Later on, other students can add new items or commentaries to the line of argumentation.

Figure 7. Environment Student. Data channels.

Figure 8. Interface to group items in lines of argumentation.

The lines of argumentation created this way can be later visualized by selecting LINEAS in the menu. The names of the lines appear listed on the vertical menu on the right. To visualize a line, its name must be dragged inside the channel space (Figure 9)

Figure 9. Display of the lines of work.

Students use this interface to search for associations and to build up working hypothesis that –after being debated in the class with peers and professors- will be developed further with other media, like photomontages, animations and multimedia presentations (Figures 10-12)

Figure 10. Economic growth

Figure 11. Global commerce.

Figure 12. Barcelona Theme park.

A selection of the topics debated in the class is exposed in the external viewer, so that all citizens can see them. In order to explain their ideas to a non-specialized audience, students must make the additional effort to make them intelligible in a common language, taking advantage of the capacities of the media.

5. Net City Installation

To conclude the activities of the workshop, the results were shown in the exhibition "eme3Density" taking place at the Centre de Cultura Contemporània de Barcelona, in November 2001 (Figures 13-14). The installation consisted of a CD Rom plus a participative action. The CD displayed the data items as automatically generated sequences, in accordance with the associations previously established in the web system. In this context, visitors were asked to express a personal view of the city by sticking ready-made images and keywords on the metal panels of the installation.

Figures 13-14. NET.CITY, installation in CCCB.

6. Conclusions

We have created a pedagogic structure, linking theoretical background, practical analysis, and information and communication technologies, to create a learning space where citizens, students and professors can construct together an understanding of their urban environment. The most critical aspect of the experience, however, has not been conceiving and implementing the learning structure but carrying it out successfully. In this regard, the most discouraging outcome of the workshop was the low level of citizen participation. The reasons for this lack of engagement would have been: 1. For many citizens, the media might have been more a deterrent than a vehicle to enhance communication. Even though we simplified the interaction and reduced the requested input to the minimum (a text and an image), for many people participating in this web environment might have seem too complicated. 2. We relied excessively on the web to promote a debate on the urban environment. In rather academic topics like this one, it is difficult to gain spontaneous participation from users, just by hanging a web page in the Internet. It is necessary to conduct other activities like group meetings, talks, group actions, in parallel to the web-based work. This way, the web-based system would be placed within a context that gives it the sense which does not necessarily have by itself 3. We have underestimated the cultural level that citizens need to be able to express a personal view of the urban environment. Without teaching them first some basic notions on urban perception, they would be unable to give their opinion on the questions we formulated.

On the other hand, the most fruitful outcome has come from the student participation and the results they produced. Through the active engagement in the workshop, students understood the link between modes of representation and modes of understanding the city. Besides, they were able to convey an image of the city, collaboratively created, which was expressed through the language of the media.

We expect to conduct future editions of the workshop at the international level, selecting case studies from different countries, with the participation of citizens, students and professors from different institutions across Europe.

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